

Modular Institutional Instrument (MII)

A Focus Group Guide for Exploring Digital Transformation in Rural Municipalities

Marcel Patalon

South Westphalia University of Applied Sciences, Germany
patalon.marcel@fh-swf.de

Version: v2.0 (May 2025) | License: CC BY 4.0
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18743986

*Keywords: Digital Transformation · Rural Municipalities · Institutional Theory · Action Design
Research · Focus Groups · Public Sector Innovation*

How to cite: Patalon, M. (2026). Modular Institutional Instrument (MII): A Focus Group Guide for Exploring Digital Transformation in Rural Municipalities. Zenodo. CC BY 4.0. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18743986>

1. Introduction

This Modular Institutional Instrument (MII) was developed as part of a doctoral research project examining the institutional dynamics of digital transformation (DT) in rural municipalities. The guide is grounded in neo-institutional theory, which emphasizes that organizational behavior in the public sector is not driven purely by efficiency or technical necessity, but is shaped by institutional environments that promote conformity, legitimacy, and stability (Greenwood et al., 2017; Scott, 2008). Specifically, the MII operationalizes the concept of institutional isomorphism (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983), which identifies three mechanisms through which organizations tend to align with their institutional environment:

- **Coercive** pressures arising from legal mandates, policy requirements, and funding conditions;
- **Mimetic** pressures resulting from uncertainty and the emulation of perceived best practices;
- **Normative** pressures stemming from professional norms, training, and networks.

These dynamics are particularly relevant in rural municipalities (Patalon & Wyczisk, 2024), which face unique challenges such as resource scarcity, demographic shifts, and fragmented administrative structures (Løken, 2021; Rembeci, 2022; Schaffert & Steensen, 2024). Understanding digital transformation in these contexts requires tools that capture both institutional complexity and local experience (Burton-Jones et al., 2020; Mahula et al., 2022).

The MII was developed through an Action Design Research (ADR) process (Sein et al., 2011) comprising iterative Alpha and Beta cycles across six focus groups with 30 practitioners from 25 municipalities in the South Westphalia region in Germany. This process yielded three formalized design principles that structure both the instrument's architecture and its facilitation logic:

- **Theory-Driven Modularity:** the instrument's modules are anchored in coercive, mimetic, and normative institutional pressures from the outset, ensuring structured inquiry across heterogeneous governance settings.
- **Reciprocal Translation:** abstract institutional concepts are iteratively reformulated into practitioner-accessible language without sacrificing analytic precision.
- **Visual Mediation:** actor maps, clustering cards, and a dot-voting intensity map externalize implicit institutional relationships and support cross-role interpretation.

Together, these principles reflect an institutionally dominant mode of artifact development in which interpretive engagement, legitimacy dynamics, and cross-role alignment shape the instrument's evolution, extending ADR's established IT-dominant and organization-dominant configurations (Sein et al., 2011) to the complexity of public sector governance.

The MII serves researchers and practitioners exploring the following five research questions:

- How do institutional pressures (coercive, mimetic, normative) influence digital transformation processes in rural municipalities?
- What roles do different actors play in hindering, enabling, or promoting digital transformation?
- What barriers hinder the implementation of digital initiatives in rural municipalities?
- What key factors support digital transformation in these municipalities?
- What are the main drivers behind digital transformation in these settings?

The guide consists of five flexible and interrelated phases:

- Phase 1 – Warm-up and introduction
- Phase 2 – Contextualization and local understanding of digital transformation

- Phase 3 – Exploration of actors and institutional influences
- Phase 4 – Discussion of barriers, enablers, and drivers
- Phase 5 – Reflection and forward-looking visioning

Designed as a modular and semi-structured instrument, the MII combines open-ended questions, thematic blocks, and visual elicitation tools (actor mapping, color-coded intensity mapping, dot-voting) to facilitate structured yet adaptable discussions. It is suitable for diverse group settings and can be reused across municipalities or adapted for other governance domains.

Terminology note: Throughout this guide, MII and instrument refer to the concrete focus group protocol and materials (prompts, visual scaffolds, facilitation procedures). The term guide is used when emphasizing the instrument's facilitating function in participatory settings. For the full theoretical and methodological grounding of the artifact, see the companion ADR paper. In the remainder of this document, we primarily use "instrument" to emphasize the MII's structured epistemic function, while "guide" refers to its practical facilitation use.

2. Design Principles for Effective Focus Group Implementation

The MII's facilitation logic is governed by three design principles formalized through the ADR development process. These principles explain how institutional theory was embedded into the instrument's architecture and how they interact with established best practices for focus group research.

2.1 Theory-Driven Modularity

The instrument is structured around institutional constructs from the outset. The three isomorphic pressure types (coercive, mimetic, and normative) inform module sequencing, prompt formulation, and the overall facilitation architecture. This ensures that the guide reflects the institutional environments in which municipal DT unfolds and supports structured inquiry across heterogeneous administrative settings (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983; Sein et al., 2011).

In practical terms, this principle shapes group composition and session design. Homogeneous groups (where participants share similar roles or experiences) tend to reach consensus more quickly and may require less facilitation time (Woźniak, 2022). Heterogeneous groups (comprising individuals from varied administrative backgrounds) often generate richer insights on how different institutional logics interact, but benefit from longer sessions (Morgan, 1997). A group size of 6 to 8 participants is recommended to balance diversity with meaningful individual contribution (Krueger & Casey, 2015). Session duration of 90 to 120 minutes is typically ideal for in-depth discussion across all five phases.

2.2 Reciprocal Translation

The MII was refined through successive reformulations that moved iteratively between abstract institutional concepts and practitioner language. This translation principle ensures that theoretical categories (legitimacy concerns, symbolic expectations, professional norms) become empirically discussable during data generation without reducing analytic precision. In facilitation, this means that theoretical constructs are never introduced using academic terminology. Instead, moderators use accessible framing aligned with everyday administrative experience (see Section 4.2). Prompts were systematically differentiated across ADR iterations: notably, mimetic and normative pressures, which practitioners initially conflated, were separated into distinct prompt families from version v1.3 onwards.

2.3 Visual Mediation

Visual tools are core to the MII, enabling participants to externalize institutional relationships, tensions, and interdependencies that often remain implicit in everyday work. Mapping templates, color-coded clustering cards, and the dot-voting intensity map support cross-role interpretation and facilitate shared meaning-making across diverse administrative logics. These tools function as boundary objects (Star & Griesemer, 1989) that help heterogeneous participant groups align around shared reference points.

Three primary visual scaffolds structure the MII's phases: (1) a provocation (standard text vignette or optional short video) in Phase 2 that legitimizes the discussion of barriers; (2) collaborative clustering that makes the abstract concept of DT tangible through keywords and cards; and (3) an interactive actor-intensity map in Phases 3 and 4, where participants use dot-voting to visually heat-map the perceived intensity of institutional influences.

3. Materials for Effective Focus Group Sessions

To ensure a smooth and effective facilitation of the focus group sessions, the following materials should be prepared in advance:

- **Name tags:** for participant identification and fostering informal interaction
- **Refreshments:** to create a welcoming and comfortable atmosphere
- **Audio and/or video recording device:** for accurate documentation and transcription (with prior written consent)
- **Consent forms:** signed by all participants to ensure informed participation
- **Participant information sheets:** outlining the purpose of the study, data handling, and participant rights
- **Projector or screen:** for showing the Phase 2 provocation (optional video)
- **Timer or clock:** to help keep track of session flow and time allocation
- **Digital camera or phone:** to document board outputs and mapping results for analysis (with consent)
- **Colored Post-its:** for brainstorming exercises or visual elicitation
- **Index cards:** in green (enablers/supporters), red (barriers/opponents), and blue (drivers/motivators) for categorising stakeholder roles and influences
- **Sticky dots or stickers:** for the dot-voting intensity map exercise (10 dots per participant)
- **Pens and markers:** for individual input and annotation
- **Flip chart or whiteboard:** to visualise key concepts, emerging themes, or group summaries
- **Metaplan board or pin board:** for collecting and clustering participant contributions in a visible, interactive format
- **Actor-Mapping Template (printed or drawn on metaplan board):** a pre-structured grid distinguishing internal/external actors and domains of action

All materials should be prepared for each session and tailored as needed to the size and composition of the participant group.

4. Facilitation Guidelines: Supporting Meaningful, Theory-Informed Dialogue

This section provides essential guidance for facilitating focus groups with this instrument. Effective moderation ensures that sessions run smoothly, participants feel heard and safe, and meaningful, theory-informed data is generated. The following principles are grounded in best

practices from qualitative research and are aligned with the theoretical and methodological foundations of the MII. Section 5 complements these general safeguards by explaining why the phase sequence is analytically necessary and by providing minimal operational cut-points to protect the instrument's analytic chain under real-world time constraints.

4.1 General Moderation Principles

Maintain neutrality:

Refrain from expressing personal opinions or signaling preferred responses. The moderator's role is to guide discussion, not influence it.

Foster equal participation:

Encourage quieter participants to contribute by gently inviting their input, while respectfully managing more dominant voices. Power asymmetries across administrative hierarchies can suppress open exchange; actively counteract this.

Listen actively:

Demonstrate engagement through non-verbal cues and paraphrasing. Use clarifying follow-ups such as:

- *"Could you give an example of that?"*
- *"How did that affect your department or team?"*
- *"Would others agree or see this differently?"*

Balance structure and flexibility:

While the MII follows a logical five-phase sequence, adapt the order or timing of questions to match group dynamics. The instrument is modular by design, and phases can be shortened or extended as needed.

Manage time effectively:

Aim to follow the recommended time blocks for each phase while allowing for spontaneous insights. The total recommended session duration is 90–120 minutes.

4.2 Handling Theoretical Constructs

The MII is informed by institutional theory, particularly the typology of coercive, mimetic, and normative pressures. While these concepts underpin the guide's structure, participants should never be exposed to technical terminology. Instead, use accessible framing and everyday administrative language:

Coercive pressures (e.g., mandates, rules): *"Are there external requirements—laws, regulations, or funding conditions—that force your municipality to act in specific ways when it comes to digitalization?"* (e.g., Online Access Act, EU funding guidelines)

Mimetic pressures (e.g., emulation under uncertainty): *"How do you handle situations where no clear digital solution exists? Do you look at other municipalities as models or sources of orientation?"*

Normative pressures (e.g., professional standards): *"How do training providers or professional associations shape your understanding of what good digital administration looks like? What do your colleagues or professional networks expect from you?"*

These should be framed as exploratory, non-judgmental questions, never as a test of theoretical knowledge.

A key refinement achieved during the ADR development process (v1.3) was the explicit differentiation of mimetic from normative prompts: practitioners consistently conflated peer comparison (mimetic) with professional obligation (normative) when addressed through broadly framed questions. The prompts above reflect this differentiation and should be used in sequence.

4.3 Using Visual Tools and Materials

Visual and participatory tools are core components of the MII, operationalizing the principle of Visual Mediation. Use them to enhance engagement, structure conversation, and externalize institutional relationships:

Provocation (Phase 2):

Use either the standard text vignette or an optional short video (~2–3 min) depicting an "overwhelmed administration", a fictional or composite scenario in which municipal staff struggle with fragmented digital systems, contradictory mandates, and capacity constraints. This legitimizes the subsequent discussion of barriers and prevents participants from feeling defensive about acknowledging difficulties.

Metaplan Boards:

Use for clustering responses thematically during exercises (e.g., mapping actors, barriers, drivers). This helps visualize collective thinking and fosters interaction.

Color-coded Index Cards:

- Green: Enabling/supportive actors or conditions
- Red: Hindering or resistant forces
- Blue: Driving or motivational factors

Dot-Voting Intensity Map (Phase 3/4):

After actors and pressures have been mapped on the metaplan board, distribute a fixed budget of sticky dots to each participant (10 dots per participant). Participants place dots on the actors or pressures they perceive as most intense or significant. The resulting "heat map" makes relative intensity visible across the group and reveals both convergence and divergence in institutional perception. Photograph the completed map before clearing the board.

Sticky Notes / Post-Its (Phase 2):

Particularly helpful for the DT keyword exercise. Encourage clarity and brevity: one keyword per note.

Markers and Flipcharts/Whiteboards:

Use for summarizing key insights or visualizing processes if needed. Encourage participants to read aloud what they have written on cards or notes to increase shared understanding.

4.4 Supporting Participants When They Struggle

Some topics—especially institutional dynamics, may seem abstract or unfamiliar. Help participants connect by offering examples or rephrasing:

- *"Has there been a time when your municipality had to change plans due to a new rule or funding requirement?"*
- *"What does 'digital transformation' mean in your daily work?"*
- If a participant says 'I don't know', try: *"What would your best guess or instinct say?"*

Use reassurance where appropriate, remind participants that their lived administrative experience is precisely what matters most. Abstract vocabulary can always be unpacked through concrete municipal examples.

4.5 Ethics and Psychological Safety

Reinforce a respectful, safe, and voluntary environment:

- Remind participants that there are no wrong answers.
- Ensure they know that contributions will be anonymized and used only for research purposes.
- Emphasize that they are free to pause, decline to answer, or withdraw at any time without consequence.
- Acknowledge and appreciate their time and insights at the beginning and end of the session.

4.6 Optional Follow-Up Prompts

Use these prompts when discussions slow or to deepen the dialogue:

- *"Can you compare that to a past experience?"*
- *"Would someone from another department see that differently?"*
- *"If you had the power to change one thing about the process, what would it be?"*

Such prompts encourage reflection and reveal contradictions, tensions, or shared understandings, particularly useful when probing the boundary between mimetic and normative pressures.

4.7 After the Session (Post-Moderation Checklist)

Conduct a debrief with your co-moderator or assistant immediately after the session (30–45 minutes):

- What worked particularly well?
- Which questions triggered the most engagement or confusion?
- Were there unexpected themes that emerged?
- Were there interpretive difficulties that suggest prompt revisions for the next iteration?

Check recordings:

Ensure the audio (or video) file is complete, securely stored, and labelled properly.

Collect all materials:

- Sticky notes, index cards, and visuals from boards
- Photograph of the dot-voting intensity map (with participant consent)

Document field observations:

Note atmosphere, participant dynamics, and memorable moments, particularly any instances where the modular structure required adaptation.

5. Discussion Structure and Guiding Questions

This section is addressed to researchers and advanced practitioners. It makes explicit what the five-phase structure is designed to produce analytically, not merely how it is facilitated, but why the sequence exists and what kind of institutional knowledge each phase generates. The MII is not a focus group guide in the conventional sense. It is an epistemically structured instrument for institutional inquiry. Where necessary, this section also provides concise operational cut-points and sequencing cues to protect the instrument's analytic chain under real-world time constraints.

Table 1. Analytic Logic of the Modular Institutional Instrument by Phase

Phase	Unit of Analysis	Data Form Produced	Institutional Mechanism Surfaced
1. Warm-Up	—	Social anchoring; role disclosure	Field composition: who is present, in what capacity, with what institutional identities
2. Contextualization	Semantic constructions of digital transformation	Practitioner-generated definitions and keyword constellations	Interpretive divergence as evidence of competing institutional logics (Thornton et al., 2012)
3. Actor Mapping	Actor–pressure constellations	Structured map of perceived institutional pressures by type, origin, and role	Isomorphic mechanisms made visible and spatially organized (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983)
4. Condition Analysis	Structural institutional conditions	Practitioner accounts of barriers, enablers, and drivers as structural realities	Institutional work and logic reproduction; decoupling between formal mandate and organizational capacity (Lawrence & Suddaby, 2006)
5. Synthesis	Closing priorities and reflective syntheses	Demographic context + synthesis statements + optional aspiration prompts	Reflexive legitimacy: how actors narrate what matters most under institutional constraint

Paragraph 1: Sequence as Theory

The five phases follow an analytically necessary progression: **meaning** → **actors** → **conditions** → **priorities**. This is not a facilitation choice, it is a theoretical commitment. Meaning must be established before actors can be coherently mapped, because practitioners construct actors through interpretive frames that are themselves institutionally conditioned. Actors must be mapped before conditions can be analyzed, because structural conditions are not abstract: they emerge from specific constellations of institutional pressure. And conditions must be made visible before priorities can be meaningfully synthesized, because participants can only reflect reflexively on what matters most after they have externalized the structural landscape that shapes their judgment. To reorder or abbreviate this sequence is not to shorten the instrument, it is to break the analytic chain.

Paragraph 2: Three Distinct Data Forms

The MII produces three analytically distinct data forms across its phases. Phase 2 generates semantic constructions: the vocabulary through which practitioners make sense of digital transformation locally. These constructions are not background noise, they are primary evidence of the interpretive frames through which institutional pressures are received and translated into action. Phase 3 generates actor–pressure constellations: structured representations of who exerts what kind of institutional influence, with what perceived effect. These constellations operationalize the isomorphic mechanisms of DiMaggio and Powell (1983) as participatory, visually anchored data. Phase 4 generates accounts of structural institutional conditions: the resource distributions, cultural scripts, organizational routines, and legitimacy expectations that the actor constellation produces over time. Each data form is irreducible to the others. Together, they constitute a multi-layered institutional picture that no single method, interview, survey, or document analysis, could produce alone.

Paragraph 3: Institutionally Dominant Artifact Development

The MII was developed through an Action Design Research process in which the instrument's evolution was driven not by usability failures, but by interpretive breakdowns, moments in the field where practitioners could not or would not engage with a given prompt, because the conceptual frame it assumed was not legible within their institutional context. This is what it means for artifact development to be institutionally dominant (Sein et al., 2011): the design logic responds to the institutional field, not merely to the research instrument. The progression from v0.1 to v2.0 tracks a series of such breakdowns: practitioners conflating mimetic and normative pressures (resolved by separating B4 and B5 into distinct temporal slots with explicit bridging); practitioners treating Phase 4 as a repetition of Phase 3 (resolved by eliminating color-card repetition and installing the WHO/WHAT distinction as a structural principle); and practitioners unable to engage with abstract isomorphism prompts (resolved by introducing the visual Actor-Mapping Template and the dot-voting intensity map as tangible mediators). Phase transitions in the MII are therefore not procedural handoffs, they are the sites where institutional dynamics become most visible, precisely because the transition demands a cognitive shift that not all participants find natural.

Paragraph 4: Sensemaking Infrastructure

The MII functions as sensemaking infrastructure (Weick, 1995), not merely as a data collection device. By providing a shared visual space (the Actor-Mapping Template), a common vocabulary (the pressure-type taxonomy), and a sequenced set of prompts that progressively externalize tacit institutional knowledge, the instrument creates the conditions under which distributed sensemaking can occur in real time. Participants who arrive with divergent framings of digital transformation are not simply surveyed for those divergences, they are placed in a structured situation in which divergence becomes productive: visible, discussable, and analytically significant. The boundary objects embedded in the instrument — the vignette, the template, the dot-voting heat map — each perform a specific sensemaking function: they bracket complexity, create commensurability across roles, and generate shared reference points without imposing premature consensus. This is not incidental to the instrument's design. It is the mechanism by which the MII generates institutional insight: not through extraction, but through structured, theory-anchored collective reflection.

For reviewers and methodologists: The four analytic properties described above, sequential theory-dependence, multi-form data production, institutionally dominant development, and sensemaking infrastructure function, distinguish the MII from conventional focus group guides that apply institutional theory post hoc. In the MII, institutional theory is not the analytic lens brought to the data after collection. It is the generative structure of the inquiry itself. This distinction is the instrument's primary methodological contribution.

5.1 Session Planning: Time Scenarios and Cut-Points

The MII is designed for sessions of 90–150+ minutes. The appropriate length depends on group size, role heterogeneity, and required research depth. Table 2 provides three scenarios with phase-level time allocations and explicit cut-points. Moderators should select a scenario before the session and communicate it to any co-moderators.

Table 2. Time Scenarios and Cut-Points by Phase

Phase	90 min (condensed)	120 min (standard)	150+ min (full depth)
1. Warm-Up	10 min Consent + 1-sentence intro per person	15 min Full introductions	15 min
2. Contextualization	10 min Text vignette + keyword exercise; skip optional video	20 min Optional video (or text vignette) + keyword clustering	25 min Optional video (or text vignette) + full cluster discussion
3. Actor Mapping	25 min B1 + B2 optional + B3/B4/B5; skip B6; dot-voting 5 min	40 min Full B1–B6 + dot-voting	55 min Full B1–B6 + extended dot-voting + group reading of map
4. Conditions	25 min C1 barriers only as priority; C2/C3 combined in 10 min	25 min C1 + C2 + C3 each 8 min	40 min Full C1–C3 with follow-up probes + closing map integration
5. Synthesis	10 min D1 only; skip thought experiment	15 min D0 + D1	20 min D0 + D1 + D2
CUT-POINT RULE	If running over in Phase 3: complete dot-voting and move on. Phase 3 closure is non-negotiable.	If running over in Phase 4: prioritize C1 (barriers) over C2/C3. Structural constraints are analytically most important.	Use full time only with groups of 8+ or with high heterogeneity across roles.
<p>Non-negotiable closure: Regardless of time pressure, always complete Phase 3 with the dot-voting exercise (B7) before moving to Phase 4. The intensity map is the bridge between the two phases. If time is critically short, skip B6 in Phase 3, but never skip B7.</p>			

Table 3 translates the analytic logic described above into a functional overview of the instrument's phases. Rather than detailing facilitation steps, the table summarizes each phase's primary focus, core analytic function, and the scaffolds through which institutional insight is generated.

Table 3. Phase Structure of the Modular Institutional Instrument: Facilitation Overview

Phase	Focus	Core Function & Scaffolds
1. Warm-up and introductions	–	Establish Safety: Introduction of participants and clarification of roles to ensure psychological safety. Tool: Introductory round (Name, Role, Relation to Municipality).
2. Contextualization and local understanding of digital transformation	Local Rationality / Legitimacy / Sensemaking	Provocation: Text vignette (standard) or optional short video showing 'overwhelmed administration' to trigger barrier discussion.

Phase	Focus	Core Function & Scaffolds
		<p>Definition: Collaborative clustering to define what 'Digital Transformation' means locally.</p> <p>Tool: Sticky-note keyword exercise + metaplan clustering.</p> <p>Transition: Explicit bridge linking local DT understanding to actor landscape.</p>
3. Exploration of actors and institutional influences	Coercive, Mimetic, Normative Pressures → WHO shapes the landscape?	<p>Actor Mapping: Participants identify and categorize actors by institutional pressure type and role (enabler/barrier/driver).</p> <p>Closure: Dot-voting intensity map weights perceived actor influence.</p> <p>Tool: Actor-Mapping Template, color-coded cards, pressure prompts.</p> <p>Output: A shared map of the institutional actor landscape — the foundation for Phase 4.</p>
4. Discussion of barriers, enablers, and drivers	Institutional Logics / Institutional Work → WHAT conditions does this landscape produce?	<p>Condition Analysis: Starting from the actor map, participants identify structural conditions — resource gaps, cultural resistances, capacity supports, strategic motivations — independent of individual actors. No color-card repeat. Discussion structured by condition type.</p> <p>Tool: Moderated dialogue using Phase 3 map as reference.</p> <p>Transition: Closing map integration bridges into Phase 5.</p>
5. Reflection and forward-looking visioning	Synthesis / Feedback	<p>Synthesis: Demographic questionnaire (D0), closing reflection (D1), optional thought experiment (D2). Tool: Printed demographic questionnaire + flipchart synthesis.</p>

5.2 Phase 1 – Warm-Up and Introduction

This phase establishes rapport, clarifies the purpose of the discussion, and creates a respectful, inclusive environment. It fulfils both ethical and methodological functions: it ensures informed consent, sets the tone for open participation, and allows for initial social anchoring among participants.

5.2.1 Welcome and Introduction of the Project

"Good [morning/afternoon], and thank you for joining today's focus group. My name is [Name], and I will be moderating this session. I am part of a research team conducting a study on digital transformation in rural municipalities. Our aim is to better understand how local actors perceive digital transformation, experience institutional pressures, and navigate challenges in implementing digital projects. Your insights today will contribute to the development of more context-sensitive and evidence-based strategies for supporting municipalities in their digital efforts."

5.2.2 Informed Consent and Confidentiality

"Before we begin, I would like to inform you that this session is part of a research project conducted in accordance with established ethical guidelines. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you may withdraw at any point without consequences. With your permission,

the session will be audio recorded solely for transcription and analysis purposes. All data will be anonymized, and no identifiable information will appear in the results."

Distribute and collect signed consent forms before proceeding.

5.2.3 Ground Rules for Discussion

Communicate the following ground rules to the group:

- Please allow each participant to speak without interruption.
- We encourage diverse opinions—there are no right or wrong answers.
- We aim for equal speaking time, so feel free to share your views while also giving others space to contribute.
- Everything discussed here remains confidential and will be used only for research purposes.

5.2.4 Participant Introductions

"To get started, we would like to do a quick round of introductions. Please tell us your name, your current role or profession, and briefly describe your connection to the municipality—whether you work there, represent a particular organization, or are otherwise involved in local affairs."

Proceed with introductions in a structured round. This warm-up phase concludes with a smooth transition to Phase 2.

5.3 Phase 2 – Contextualization and Local Understanding of Digital Transformation

This phase establishes a shared conceptual baseline by eliciting participants' interpretations of digital transformation within their municipal context. It combines a provocation with a collaborative keyword exercise. The provocation reduces defensiveness before the more analytically demanding phases begin; the keyword exercise surfaces semantic variability that reveals different institutional logics before they are named as such.

5.3.1 Provocation: “The Overwhelmed Administration”

Objective:

To activate a shared frame of reference and legitimize the discussion of barriers and difficulties. The provocation signals that acknowledging problems is expected and valuable, and not a sign of failure. It functions as a boundary object (Star & Griesemer, 1989) that allows practitioners from different roles to project their own experience onto a shared scenario.

Standard Text Vignette (read aloud or project on screen):

It is a Tuesday morning in the municipal administration of a medium-sized rural town. The head of department has just received a reminder from the state ministry: the deadline for implementing the Online Access Act is in six weeks. She opens her inbox to find 47 unread messages — most of them about a citizen portal that has been under development for two years and still does not work properly. The IT department consists of one full-time and one part-time employee. The full-time employee has been seconded to a neighboring municipality for a joint digital transformation project. The part-time employee does not know the login credentials for the portal system — they were managed by a colleague who left three months ago and has not been replaced. In the afternoon, there is a meeting of the municipal council. Three councilors want a status report on the Smart City strategy approved 18 months ago. The head of department has not had time to prepare one. The digital strategy officer — a new position funded by a two-year state grant — is on sick leave. The grant runs out in four months. Meanwhile, a neighboring

municipality has just won a digital transformation award and is featured in the regional newspaper. A councilor forwards the article with a single comment: “Why can’t we do this?”

Moderator Instructions:

“I have just read you a short scenario. It is fictional — but perhaps not entirely unfamiliar. Take a moment to react: what did you recognize? What resonated — or did not resonate — with your own experience?”

Allow 5–7 minutes of open reaction before transitioning to the keyword exercise. Do not interpret the vignette. The aim is to open the space, not anchor the discussion.

Note to Moderators: A video version is optional (2–3 min). The text vignette is the standard and requires no additional production. In the 90-minute scenario: use this text vignette (do not skip the provocation entirely), then proceed directly to the keyword exercise.

5.3.2 Collaborative Clustering: Defining Digital Transformation

Section	Guiding Question	Activity	Materials
A1. Understanding of Digital Transformation	What does digital transformation mean in the context of your municipality?	Participants write keywords on sticky notes and briefly explain.	Sticky notes, pens

Objective:

To elicit individual and shared interpretations of “digital transformation” within the municipal context and to capture semantic variability as a foundation for theory-informed discussion.

Moderator Instructions:

“Let’s begin by exploring what digital transformation means in your municipality. Please take a few minutes to write down some keywords or short phrases on the sticky notes — one keyword per note. We will then cluster them together on the board.”

After collection, cluster similar responses on the metaplan board to visualize emerging themes. Briefly narrate the clusters aloud to confirm shared interpretation.

Note to Moderators: Avoid framing digital transformation too narrowly. Divergences in how practitioners define DT often reveal different institutional logics at work. These divergences are analytically valuable, not problems to be resolved.

Transition: Phase 2 → Phase 3

Transition script (read aloud): *“We now have a picture of what digital transformation means in this municipality — and already we can see that different people emphasize different things: some focused on technology, others on processes, others on culture or politics. That diversity is not random. It reflects the different pressures and expectations that each of you faces in your role. In the next part of our session, we want to map those pressures more systematically — not by asking what digital transformation is, but who shapes it: which actors, organizations, and institutions influence how digitalization unfolds here, and in which direction.”*

5.4 Phase 3 – Exploration of Actors and Institutional Influences

Core analytical question: WHO shapes the institutional landscape of municipal digital transformation — and through which type of pressure?

Phase 3 focuses exclusively on actors and the institutional pressures they exert. Its output is a shared visual map — the Actor-Mapping Template — that shows who is involved, what type of pressure they exercise, and whether they are perceived as enablers, barriers, or drivers. This map becomes the explicit foundation for Phase 4.

Table 4 shows the structure of the template as it should appear on the metaplan board. Each cell holds color-coded actor cards. Dot stickers are added during B7 (Phase 3 closure).

Table 4. Actor-Mapping Template — Reference Layout (use as basis for metaplan board preparation)

Pressure Type	INTERNAL ACTORS <i>Within the municipal administration</i>	EXTERNAL ACTORS <i>Outside the municipality</i>
Formal & Legal Level COERCIVE	<i>e.g. Mayor's office, Legal dept., IT compliance officer</i> [GREEN / RED / BLUE cards] ●●● dot-voting	<i>e.g. Federal/State legislature, OZG, EU funding bodies, supervisory authorities</i> [GREEN / RED / BLUE cards] ●●● dot-voting
Peer Orientation & Benchmarking MIMETIC	<i>e.g. CDO, project leads, Smart City team</i> [GREEN / RED / BLUE cards] ●●● dot-voting	<i>e.g. Neighbouring municipalities, Smart City leaders, consultancies, media</i> [GREEN / RED / BLUE cards] ●●● dot-voting
Professionalism & Norms NORMATIVE	<i>e.g. Administrative specialists, trained civil servants, HR</i> [GREEN / RED / BLUE cards] ●●● dot-voting	<i>e.g. Municipal employers' associations, admin. schools, IT professional bodies</i> [GREEN / RED / BLUE cards] ●●● dot-voting
Cross-Cutting / Open MIXED	<i>e.g. Council members, citizens' advisory boards</i> [GREEN / RED / BLUE cards] ●●● dot-voting	<i>e.g. Civil society, citizens, media, private sector, inter-municipal networks</i> [GREEN / RED / BLUE cards] ●●● dot-voting

Preparation note: Before the session, draw this grid on a large metaplan board (minimum A1 format). Label rows and columns clearly with adhesive labels.

5.4.1 Phase 3 Opening: Regional Context (Contextual Framing)

Objective:

Before beginning actor mapping, briefly contextualize the institutional landscape for this specific region. This is not a separate analytical section. It is an orientation step that helps participants calibrate which actors are present, absent, or differently weighted compared to urban settings.

Why this appears here, not later: In earlier versions of the MII, “Regional Conditions” appeared as a parallel section alongside the pressure-type discussions (B3–B6), creating the misleading impression that “rural location” is a fourth type of institutional pressure. It is not. Rural location is a contextual condition that modulates all three pressure types. It is therefore addressed as a framing step before the actor mapping begins.

Moderator Instructions:

"Before we begin mapping actors, let's briefly consider your specific context. How does being a rural municipality in South Westphalia shape the actor landscape? Which actors or resources that might exist in urban settings are absent here — and which cooperative structures or inter-municipal arrangements are particularly strong?"

Note key points on a flip chart. This context informs how participants populate the actor map in B1–B6.

Table 5 presents the core prompts for each pressure type alongside the associated visual scaffolds. These prompts are organized by isomorphic mechanism. They are not interchangeable and should be used in the subsections indicated, not recombined or reordered.

Table 5. Sample Prompts and Scaffolds by Institutional Pressure Type (Phase 3)

Pressure Type	Guiding Questions (Sample)	Visual / Tangible Scaffold
Coercive (External Mandates)	<i>"Are there external requirements—laws, regulations, or funding conditions—that force you to act?" "What happens if you do not comply?"</i>	Clustering: Participants write perceived constraints (e.g., 'Online Access Act', 'IT service provider mandate') on cards and mark them by intensity.
Mimetic (Uncertainty / Emulation)	<i>"How do you handle situations where no clear digital solution exists?" "Do you look at other municipalities as models or sources of orientation?"</i>	Comparative Mapping: Identifying 'peer' municipalities or 'best practices' on the metaplan board (e.g., noting which neighboring towns participants emulate and why).
Normative (Professionalization)	<i>"How do training providers shape your understanding of what good digital administration looks like?" "What do your colleagues or professional associations expect from you?"</i>	Role Reflection: Discussing professional standards and 'cultural' expectations within the administration.

Table 6 translates the theoretical structure of Phase 3 into a sequential session plan. Each row corresponds to one moderator move: a guiding question, the associated activity on the Actor-Mapping Template, and the materials required.

Table 6. Phase 3 Session Plan: Actor-Mapping Sequence (B1–B7)

Section	Guiding Question	Activity	Materials
B1. Identifying stakeholders + role colour assignment	<i>"Which actors are involved in DT projects?" Are they enablers (green), barriers (red), or drivers (blue)?"</i>	Participants write one actor per card, select colour, and place on template (row/column assignment can be provisional).	Index cards (all colours), Actor-Mapping Template
B2. Scope anchor (optional)	<i>"Which DT initiatives or domains are in scope today (e.g., citizen services, internal processes, data, infrastructure)?"</i>	Quick inventory (3–5 items) on flipchart to anchor later actor placement.	Flipchart/whiteboard, markers
B3. Coercive Pressures	<i>"Do you feel pressure from state/federal mandates? Which actors are the source?"</i>	Assign/complete actors in the COERCIVE row; add missing actors if needed.	—
B4. Normative Pressures	<i>"How do professional associations or training</i>	Assign/complete actors in the NORMATIVE row;	—

Section	Guiding Question	Activity	Materials
	<i>bodies shape your approach?"; "Which actors transmit these expectations?"</i>	add missing actors if needed.	
B5. Mimetic Pressures	<i>"Which actors do you look to as role models or sources of orientation when no solution is clear?"</i>	Assign/complete actors in the MIMETIC row; add missing actors if needed.	—
B6. External Expectations	<i>"Beyond legal requirements: are there actors whose expectations (political, public, reputational) influence your digital transformation?"</i>	Assign/complete actors in appropriate rows (often MIXED); add missing actors if needed.	—
B7. Dot-Voting (non-negotiable closure)	<i>"Which actors on the map exert the most intense influence — positively or negatively?"</i>	10 dots per participant (fixed budget). Photograph completed map before proceeding.	Dot stickers (10 per person)

Sections B3–B6 can be reordered if the group's discussion makes a different sequence more natural, but all should be covered in the standard (120 min) and full-depth (150+ min) scenarios. B1 is always first. B7 is always last.

B1. Identifying Stakeholders and Actor Roles

Objective:

To populate the Actor-Mapping Template with the full range of relevant actors, each categorized by role (card color), pressure type (row), and origin (column) — treated as three independent decisions.

Moderator Instructions:

"Let's begin by identifying the actors involved in digital transformation efforts in your municipality. Write one actor per card. For each actor, we will make three decisions together: what color card — green, red, or blue — best describes their role? Which row fits the type of pressure they exert? And are they internal or external?"

Walk participants through the first two or three actors explicitly, demonstrating all three placement decisions. Then let the group proceed independently.

Redirection prompt: If participants list structural problems rather than actors (e.g., 'lack of funding', 'slow procurement'), redirect: *"That is an important condition — we will come back to it in the next Phase. For now: who is the actor connected to that issue? Let's put them on the map."*

B2. Scope Anchor (Optional)

Objective:

To reduce ambiguity in actor naming by briefly anchoring which digital transformation domains or initiatives the discussion refers to.

Moderator Instructions:

"Before we go deeper, let's quickly note which digital transformation initiatives or domains we implicitly talk about today — just as a shared anchor. This is not an evaluation; it helps us keep the mapping consistent."

Keep it short (3–5 items). Skip in 90-minute sessions if needed.

B3. Coercive Pressures

Moderator Instructions:

"Are there external requirements — laws, regulations, or funding conditions — that force your municipality to act in specific ways? Which actors are the source? Add them to the COERCIVE row if they are not already there."

B4. Normative Pressures

Moderator Instructions:

"How do training providers or professional associations shape your understanding of good digital administration? Which actors transmit these professional expectations? Add them to the NORMATIVE row."

B5. Mimetic Pressures

Moderator Instructions:

"How do you handle situations where no clear digital solution exists? Which actors do you look to as models or sources of orientation? Add them to the MIMETIC row."

Facilitation note: Keep B4 and B5 clearly separate. Practitioners often conflate professional obligation (normative) with peer emulation (mimetic). If needed: *"We are asking here specifically about looking to others for orientation — not about professional standards, but about which municipalities you follow when uncertain."*

B6. External Expectations

Moderator Instructions:

"Beyond legal requirements, are there actors — the public, politicians, media — whose expectations informally influence your municipality's digital efforts? Add them in the row that best fits the type of pressure they represent."

B7. Dot-Voting: Closing Phase 3 (Non-Negotiable)

Objective:

To close Phase 3 by collectively weighting actor intensity, producing a heat map that serves as the explicit bridge to Phase 4.

Moderator Instructions:

"We now have a picture of the actors shaping digital transformation here. Before we move on: each of you receives ten dot stickers. Place your dots on the actors you perceive as most intensely influential — positive or negative. You can concentrate them or spread them."

Read the heat map aloud: name the top three or four actors and note their color and position. Then transition explicitly:

"Thank you — this gives us a shared picture of who shapes the landscape and which actors feel most intense. Now I'd like to shift our focus. Phase 4 will not be about the actors themselves, but about the structural conditions they produce: the resource gaps, cultural habits, and organizational routines that shape your daily work regardless of who holds a particular role. That is what we explore next."

Photograph the map: Take a photograph of the completed dot-voting map before moving on. This is independent data that should be preserved regardless of the transcript.

5.5 Phase 4 – Discussion of Barriers, Enablers, and Drivers

Core analytical question: WHAT structural conditions does the institutional landscape — mapped in Phase 3 — produce for digital transformation in practice?

Phase 4 shifts the unit of analysis from actors to conditions. Where Phase 3 asked “*who shapes the landscape?*”, Phase 4 asks “*what does that landscape produce in practice?*” The focus is on structural barriers, enabling conditions, and motivational forces that exist independently of individual actors, emerging from the interplay of institutional pressures over time. This distinction is grounded in institutional logics (Thornton et al., 2012) and institutional work (Lawrence & Suddaby, 2006). Institutional logics manifest as structural conditions: resource distributions, cultural scripts, organizational routines, and legitimacy expectations. Phase 4 makes these conditions visible through structured discussion anchored in the Phase 3 map.

What Phase 4 is NOT: Phase 4 does not repeat the color-card exercise from Phase 3. No new green/red/blue cards. The Actor-Mapping Template remains visible as a reference, but participants are asked to abstract from “who” to “what”. If participants name an actor, redirect: “That is the actor — what condition does their presence or absence create?”

Open Phase 4 by pointing to the dot-voting map from Phase 3:

“We now have a shared picture of who shapes digital transformation here and which actors feel most intense. Let’s use that as a springboard. Rather than the actors themselves, I’d like us to look at the conditions they create: what structural realities — resource gaps, cultural habits, organizational routines, financial pressures — make digital transformation harder or easier, regardless of who occupies a particular role?”

Phase 4 is structured around three analytically distinct condition types, each corresponding to a different dimension of the institutional landscape. Table 7 sets out the guiding question and analytical focus for each. The three sections are designed to be cumulative: C1 (barriers) establishes what makes progress difficult, C2 (enablers) identifies what is already working despite those barriers, and C3 (drivers) surfaces the forces that make change feel necessary or urgent regardless of current capacity. Together, they produce a structural account of the conditions the actor landscape from Phase 3 generates in practice.

Table 7. Phase 4: From Actor Landscape to Structural Conditions

Section	Analytical Focus	Guiding Question	Key Distinction from Phase 3
C1. Barriers (Structural constraints)	Resource gaps, capacity deficits, cultural resistance, institutional inertia	<i>“Looking at the actor map we just built — what structural conditions do these actors and pressures create that make DT harder? Think about resources, capacity, culture, and organizational routines.”</i>	Phase 3: WHO creates pressure e.g. “the state via OAA” Phase 4: WHAT condition results e.g. “compliance absorbs all available IT capacity”

Section	Analytical Focus	Guiding Question	Key Distinction from Phase 3
C2. Enablers (Structural supports)	Existing capacities, supportive structures, relational resources, institutional legitimacy	<i>"Which structural conditions — independent of individual goodwill — actually make digital transformation possible here? What is already in place that helps?"</i>	Phase 3: WHO enables e.g. 'the CDO' Phase 4: WHAT condition enables e.g. 'an established inter-municipal data-sharing agreement'
C3. Drivers (Motivational forces)	Strategic imperatives, value commitments, demographic pressures, citizen expectations	<i>"What forces — not just people — are pushing your municipality toward DT even when it is difficult? What makes it feel necessary or urgent?"</i>	Phase 3: WHO drives e.g. 'Smart City network peers' Phase 4: WHAT drives e.g. 'demographic decline making traditional service delivery unsustainable'

C1. Barriers — Structural Constraints

Objective:

Identify structural conditions, resource deficits, capacity gaps, cultural resistance, institutional inertia, that result from the actor constellation in Phase 3 but cannot be reduced to any single actor.

Moderator Instructions:

"Looking at the actor map — what structural conditions do these actors and their pressures create that make digital transformation harder? Think about budgets, staffing, skills gaps, procurement rules, cultural habits, political cycles."

Follow-up prompts:

- *"Which conditions would persist even if the key people changed? Those are the structural ones."*
- *"Are there capacity gaps — technical, financial, or time-based — that cut across multiple projects?"*
- *"Are there unspoken rules in your administration that make digital experimentation difficult?"*
- *"What happens to digital initiatives when they hit procurement law, data protection, or budget cycles?"*
- *"Have you shifted any of these conditions in the past? What did it take?"*

C2. Enablers — Structural Supports

Objective:

Surface structural conditions, existing capacities, relational resources, legitimacy, organizational arrangements, that enable digital transformation independently of individual goodwill.

Moderator Instructions:

"What structural conditions — not individual champions, but actual capacities, agreements, or frameworks — genuinely make digital transformation easier here?"

Follow-up prompts:

- *"Are there inter-municipal agreements or shared platforms that reduce the burden on your municipality?"*
- *"Is there an established legitimacy for digital projects that makes approval or resourcing easier?"*
- *"Are there reliable funding streams independent of political cycles?"*

- *"What organizational routines — regular formats, review processes, team structures — actively support digital work?"*

C3. Drivers — Motivational Forces

Objective:

Identify structural and societal forces, demographic pressures, citizen expectations, fiscal constraints, value commitments, that make digital transformation feel necessary at the organizational level, beyond individual motivation.

Moderator Instructions:

"What forces — not people, but structural and societal realities — are pushing your municipality toward digital transformation even when it is difficult? What makes it feel unavoidable or urgent?"

Follow-up prompts:

- *"How does demographic change — aging population, rural outmigration — shape the urgency of DT?"*
- *"Are there fiscal pressures that make digital efficiency a necessity rather than a choice?"*
- *"How do citizen expectations — especially from younger residents — create pressure on your service offer?"*
- *"Is there a broader narrative about what a 'modern municipality' looks like that shapes what you feel you need to do?"*

Closing Phase 4: Map Integration

Before transitioning to Phase 5, briefly connect the conditions named in Phase 4 back to the actor map on the board. Point to specific actors and name the conditions they were found to produce. This closes the analytical loop.

Transition: Phase 4 to Phase 5

Transition script (read aloud): *"We have now mapped both the actors shaping digital transformation here and the structural conditions they produce. Together, these give us a fairly complete picture of the institutional landscape your municipality operates in. For our final phase, I'd like to step back from analysis and give each of you the chance to reflect: given everything we have discussed — the actors, the pressures, the conditions — what do you take away as the single most important insight or priority? We will also ask you to fill in a short questionnaire to help us understand the context of your responses."*

5.6 Phase 5 – Reflection and Forward-Looking Visioning

The concluding phase collects demographic context data (D0), synthesizes insights from all four preceding phases (D1), and optionally engages participants in a forward-looking thought experiment (D2).

Table 8. Phase 5 Closing Activities

Section	Guiding Question	Activity	Materials
D0. Demographic Questionnaire (opens Phase 5)	See Appendix A.	Distribute printed questionnaire. Participants complete individually (5 min). Collect before D1.	Printed questionnaire (Appendix A), pens

Section	Guiding Question	Activity	Materials
D1. Reflection	<i>"From everything we've discussed, what do you believe is the most important factor for successful digital transformation in rural municipalities?"</i>	Each participant shares one key takeaway. Record on flipchart.	Flipchart / metaplan, pens
D2. Thought Experiment (Optional)	<i>"Imagine you had unlimited resources to support digital transformation. What would you change—and why?"</i>	Use only if time allows. One idea per card, brief justification.	Index cards or sticky notes, markers

D0. Demographic Questionnaire

Objective:

To collect participant background data that contextualizes their contributions and enables comparison across focus groups. Administered at the start of Phase 5, after the main discussion and before the closing reflection, to avoid priming participants with analytical categories.

Moderator Instructions:

Distribute the printed questionnaire from Appendix A. Allow 5 minutes for individual completion. Collect all forms before proceeding to D1.

Why D0 is placed here, not at the start: Administering the questionnaire at the start of the session risks priming participants with categories (municipality size, years of experience) before the discussion begins. Placing it at the start of Phase 5 preserves the organic quality of Phases 2–4 while still capturing background data before the session closes.

D1. Reflection: Identifying the Most Important Factor

Objective:

To consolidate the discussion by inviting each participant to articulate what they perceive as the single most important factor for successful digital transformation, drawing on the full arc of the session.

Moderator Instructions:

"Based on everything we have discussed — the actors, the pressures, the structural conditions — what do you believe is the single most important factor for enabling digital transformation in your municipality? Please take a moment to think, then we will go around once."

Record answers on a flipchart. Briefly reflect the pattern back: convergences and divergences. This is a synthesis, not an evaluation.

D2. Thought Experiment (Optional)

Objective:

To surface underlying aspirations and strategic priorities by temporarily removing the structural constraints Phase 4 made visible, creating productive dissonance.

Moderator Instructions:

"Imagine your municipality had unlimited resources — funding, staffing, and time — to support digital transformation. What would you change, and why? Please write one specific idea on an index card."

Invite volunteers to share and briefly justify. The contrast between Phase 4 barriers and the aspirations voiced here is analytically significant.

Note to Moderators: If participants anchor heavily on Phase 4 constraints even here, acknowledge it: "It is interesting that even in this thought experiment, the same conditions keep coming up — that tells us something about how deeply structural they feel."

6. From Insight to Action: Reflections and Future Use

The MII represents more than a data collection tool: it is a bridge between theoretical inquiry and practical reflection. Grounded in institutional theory and developed through an Action Design Research process across six iterative focus groups, the instrument translates complex institutional dynamics into structured, participatory group discussions. By operationalizing coercive, mimetic, and normative pressures through the design principles of Theory-Driven Modularity, Reciprocal Translation, and Visual Mediation, it enables researchers and practitioners to explore how local actors experience, interpret, and navigate digital transformation in rural governance settings. The co-creation process with municipal stakeholders in South Westphalia, Germany—spanning an Alpha cycle of prototype development and a Beta cycle of field-based evaluation—ensures that the MII is not only theoretically robust but also context-sensitive and user-oriented. As a result, it supports rich, comparative insights while remaining adaptable to the diverse realities of rural administrations. The modular five-phase structure provides consistency across cases alongside flexibility for local adaptation.

6.1 Key Strengths

Empirical Depth:

The MII fosters meaningful conversations about the underlying logics of digital change, capturing not only observable practices but also perceptions, constraints, and aspirations.

Theoretical Integration:

By embedding institutional theory directly into the discussion structure and facilitation sequence, the guide enables ex ante alignment between research design and data interpretation. The explicit differentiation of mimetic from normative prompts, a key refinement from the ADR cycles, prevents conflation of peer emulation with professional obligation.

Practical Relevance:

Through participatory techniques, actor mapping, color-coded cards, and the dot-voting intensity map, the MII empowers municipalities to engage in self-assessment, strategic dialogue, and capacity-building.

Transferability:

While tailored to the South Westphalian context, the MII's design principles are applicable to governance environments in other regions and domains, including education, sustainability, and public health.

6.2 Recommended Use Cases

This guide can be employed in various settings:

- Academic research projects focused on public sector innovation, digital governance, or institutional change
- Municipal workshops or peer-learning formats seeking to reflect on digital transformation maturity, actor constellations, or strategy development

- Policy consultations and network meetings where structured input from diverse stakeholders is required
- Training settings for digital officers, administrative leaders, or interdisciplinary teams engaged in transformation processes

6.3 Opportunities for Further Development

The MII is designed to evolve through continued use and feedback. Future enhancements may include:

- Module extensions for algorithmic governance and AI-mediated decision-making in public administration, building on the MII's emphasis on visual mediation and cross-role dialogue to make the institutional implications of AI tangible and discussable
- Sector-specific adaptations for areas such as health, education, or environmental governance
- Digital integration, such as online whiteboards or hybrid focus group formats, to expand accessibility
- Cross-national applications to explore how institutional pressures vary across different administrative cultures and political systems
- Mixed-method integration, pairing the MII with surveys, ethnographic work, or AI-supported transcript analysis for deeper insight

6.4 Final Note

As municipalities across Europe and beyond grapple with the challenges of digital transformation, tools like the MII are vital for fostering shared understanding, strategic coordination, and evidence-based action. By operationalizing an institutionally dominant mode of artifact development, one shaped by legitimacy dynamics, interpretive engagement, and cross-role alignment rather than by technical optimization alone. The instrument contributes to more inclusive, informed, and adaptive approaches to digital transformation in the public sector.

References

- Burton-Jones, A., Akhlaghpour, S., Ayre, S., Barde, P., Staib, A., & Sullivan, C. (2020). Changing the conversation on evaluating digital transformation in healthcare: Insights from an institutional analysis. *Information and Organization*, 30(1), 100255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.INFOANDORG.2019.100255>
- DiMaggio, P. J., & Powell, W. W. (1983). The Iron Cage Revisited: Institutional Isomorphism and Collective Rationality in Organizational Fields. *American Sociological Review*, 48(2), 147. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2095101>
- Greenwood, R., Oliver, C., Lawrence, T., & Meyer, R. (2017). *The SAGE Handbook of Organizational Institutionalism*. SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781526415066>
- Krueger, R. A., & Casey, M. A. (2015). *Focus groups: A practical guide for applied research* (5th edition). SAGE.
- Lawrence, T., & Suddaby, R. (2006). Institutions and Institutional Work. In S. Clegg, C. Hardy, T. Lawrence, & W. Nord (Eds.), *The SAGE Handbook of Organization Studies* (pp. 215–254). SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781848608030.n7>
- Løken, T. D. (2021). Organizing financial resources in the municipality: a case study on integrated services provision to persons with dual diagnosis. *International Journal of Integrated Care*, 21(S1), 119. <https://doi.org/10.5334/IJIC.ICIC20289>
- Mahula, S., Lindquist, M., Norström, L., & Lindman, J. (2022). Digital transformation in local government organisations: empirical evidence from blockchain initiatives. In L. Hagen, M. Solvak, & S. Hwang (Eds.), *DG.O 2022: The 23rd Annual International Conference on*

- Digital Government Research* (pp. 336–345). ACM.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3543434.3543474>
- Morgan, D. (1997). *Focus Groups as Qualitative Research*. SAGE Publications, Inc.
<https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412984287>
- Patalon, M., & Wyczisk, A. (2024). Mapping Digital Transformation of Municipalities through the Lens of Institutional Isomorphism. *International Journal on Social and Education Sciences*, 6(4), 600–635. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijonses.701>
- Rembeci, G. (2022). The Territorial Reform and its Impact to Demographic Profile of New Municipalities in Albania. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Research and Development*, 9(4. S2), 129. <https://doi.org/10.56345/ijrdv9n4s221>
- Schaffert, M., & Steensen, T. (2024). Demographic transition in aging neighborhoods: a GIS-based analysis from Germany's countryside. *Survey Review*, 56(397), 323–331.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00396265.2024.2340896>
- Scott, W. R. (2008). *Institutions and organizations: Ideas and interests* (3. ed. [Nachdr.]). SAGE.
- Sein, Henfridsson, Purao, Rossi, & Lindgren (2011). Action Design Research. *MIS Quarterly*, 35(1), 37. <https://doi.org/10.2307/23043488>
- Star, S. L., & Griesemer, J. R. (1989). Institutional Ecology, 'Translations' and Boundary Objects: Amateurs and Professionals in Berkeley's Museum of Vertebrate Zoology, 1907-39. *Social Studies of Science*, 19(3), 387–420.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/030631289019003001>
- Thornton, P. H., Ocasio, W., & Lounsbury, M. (2012). *The Institutional Logics Perspective*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199601936.001.0001>
- Woźniak, W. (2022). Homogeneity of Focus Groups as a Pathway to Successful Research Findings? Methodological Notes from the Fieldwork. *Przegląd Socjologii Jakościowej*, 10(1), 6–23. <https://doi.org/10.18778/1733-8069.10.1.01>

Appendix A: Demographic Questionnaire

Modular Institutional Instrument (MII) — Focus Group Study on Digital Transformation in Rural Municipalities

This questionnaire collects anonymous demographic and contextual information. It is completed at the start of Phase 5 of the focus group (D0) and collected by the moderation team before the closing reflection begins. All responses are treated confidentially and used exclusively for research purposes.

Part 1: Personal and Demographic Information

0. Participant ID

Assigned by the research team — please leave blank.

Participant _____	ID:	<i>To be completed by the research team. Please leave blank.</i>
-----------------------------	------------	--

1. Gender

Please tick one option.

<input type="checkbox"/> Female	<input type="checkbox"/> Male	<input type="checkbox"/> Diverse	<input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to say
---------------------------------	-------------------------------	----------------------------------	--

2. Age

Please tick one option.

<input type="checkbox"/> Student / Early career <i>under 25</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Early professional life <i>25–34</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Established career <i>35–49</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Advanced professional life <i>50–59</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Retirement age <i>60 and older</i>
--	--	---	---	--

3. Highest Level of Education

Please tick one option.

<input type="checkbox"/> No formal qualification	<input type="checkbox"/> Lower secondary school certificate	<input type="checkbox"/> Intermediate secondary school certificate
<input type="checkbox"/> University of applied sciences entrance qualification	<input type="checkbox"/> General university entrance qualification (Abitur)	<input type="checkbox"/> Vocational training qualification
<input type="checkbox"/> University degree (B.A. / M.A. / Diploma)	<input type="checkbox"/> Doctoral degree	<input type="checkbox"/> Other

Professional Background

4. At which level of public administration are you active?

Please tick one option.

<input type="checkbox"/> Municipal / City administration	<input type="checkbox"/> District administration	<input type="checkbox"/> Regional government / State administration
<input type="checkbox"/> Federal authority / Ministry	<input type="checkbox"/> Other / Private sector	

5. Which of the following positions best describes your role?

Please tick one option.

<input type="checkbox"/> Political leadership <i>e.g. Mayor, Deputy Mayor, Municipal Council Member</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Senior administrative management <i>e.g. Head of Office, Department Head, Section Leader</i>
<input type="checkbox"/> Digital transformation / IT responsibility <i>e.g. CIO, CDO, Head of IT, Smart City Manager</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Administrative staff / Specialist roles <i>e.g. Finance, Citizens' Services Office</i>
<input type="checkbox"/> External consulting / Project partner <i>e.g. Academia, Business, Economic Development</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Other position

6. What role do you play in digitalization projects in your municipality?

Multiple answers possible.

<input type="checkbox"/> Strategic decisions and budget responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/> Operational implementation and project management
<input type="checkbox"/> Technical support and IT management	<input type="checkbox"/> Advisory role / academic support
<input type="checkbox"/> Not directly involved in digitalization projects	

7. In which areas are you specifically active?

Multiple answers possible.

<input type="checkbox"/> Digital public services and citizen portals	<input type="checkbox"/> IT infrastructure and cybersecurity
<input type="checkbox"/> Open data and Smart City projects	<input type="checkbox"/> E-Government and automation of administrative processes
<input type="checkbox"/> Inter-municipal cooperation on digitalization projects	<input type="checkbox"/> Training and professional development in digitalization
<input type="checkbox"/> Other areas of activity	

Part 2: Information about Your Municipality

8. How many inhabitants does the municipality where you work have?

Please tick one option.

<input type="checkbox"/> Very small municipality <i>< 5,000 inhabitants</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Small town <i>5,000 – 19,999 inhabitants</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Medium-sized town <i>20,000 – 99,999 inhabitants</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> City <i>100,000 – 499,999 inhabitants</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Metropolitan city <i>≥ 500,000 inhabitants</i>
---	--	--	---	--

Part 3: Evaluation of the Focus Group

9. How well did you feel included in the discussion?

<input type="checkbox"/> Very well	<input type="checkbox"/> Well	<input type="checkbox"/> Neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> Not very well	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all
------------------------------------	-------------------------------	----------------------------------	--	-------------------------------------

10. How clear was the topic of the focus group to you?

<input type="checkbox"/> Very clear	<input type="checkbox"/> Fairly clear	<input type="checkbox"/> Neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather unclear	<input type="checkbox"/> Very unclear
--	--	-------------------------------------	--	--

11. How relevant was the discussion to your professional practice or field?

<input type="checkbox"/> Very relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Fairly relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather irrelevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant at all
---	---	-------------------------------------	---	---

12. How would you rate the diversity of perspectives in the discussion?

<input type="checkbox"/> Very diverse	<input type="checkbox"/> Fairly diverse	<input type="checkbox"/> Neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> Less diverse	<input type="checkbox"/> Hardly diverse
--	--	-------------------------------------	--	--

13. How did you find the moderation of the focus group?

<input type="checkbox"/> Very good	<input type="checkbox"/> Good	<input type="checkbox"/> Neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> Less than satisfactory	<input type="checkbox"/> Poor
---------------------------------------	----------------------------------	-------------------------------------	--	----------------------------------

14. How did you find the time management of the discussion?

<input type="checkbox"/> Much too long	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat too long	<input type="checkbox"/> Appropriate	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat too short	<input type="checkbox"/> Much too short
---	---	---	--	--

Content Assessment

15. What insights did you take away from the discussion?

Please note key points briefly.

16. Were there aspects you felt were insufficiently addressed?

If so, which ones?

17. Do you have suggestions for improving future focus groups?

18. Would you like to share any further comments or thoughts on the discussion?

Data Protection Notice: Your responses are stored pseudonymously (participant ID) and used exclusively for scientific analysis. Individual identification is neither possible nor intended. For further information, please refer to the participant information sheet for this study.